

TEMPORAL VARIATION IN ARRIVAL AND PRICES OF TOMATO IN MAJOR MARKETS OF INDIA.

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Abstract

The present study "Temporal Variations in Arrival and Prices of Tomato in Major Markets of India" analyzed Trends, Seasonal variations, Cyclical fluctuations, and the Relationship between Arrivals and Prices of Tomatoes in five major markets of India over the period from 2012-13 to 2022-23. Five markets were selected from major tomato producing states, i.e., Madanpalle (Andhra Pradesh), Azadpur (Delhi), Kolar (Karnataka), Pimpalgaon (Maharashtra) and Ahmedabad (Gujrat). The entire investigation relied on data obtained from secondary sources. Data on monthly wholesale prices and arrival of selected market was gathered from Agmarknet website. The data collected were subjected to statistical analysis using different methods like moving average, time series models and correlation analysis.

Results showed the mixed Trends in Arrivals and Prices. Madanpalle, Azadpur, and Pimpalgaon had stable Arrivals but significant Price growth, while Kolar saw growth in both, and Ahmedabad had declining Arrivals but rising Prices. The Coefficient of Variation indicated maximum variability in Madanpalle. The Cuddy Della Valle Index revealed more variability in Arrivals for Madanpalle, Kolar, and Pimpalgaon, and in Prices for Azadpur and Ahmedabad.

Seasonal indices indicated lowest Arrivals from February to May and highest from July to September, except in Azadpur (highest in March). Prices were lowest in February-March and highest in July. Cyclical indices showed distinct trends: Madanpalle had steady increases, Azadpur saw declines, Kolar had decreased arrivals but stable prices, Pimpalgaon had continuous declines, and Ahmedabad had rising arrivals but falling prices. Correlation analysis revealed varied relationships between arrivals and prices across markets.

Keywords: Tomato, Arrival and Prices, Price Behavior, CGR, Variability, Seasonality, Correlation.

Introduction and Objectives

Tomatoes hold a prominent position in India's agricultural landscape, both as a vital crop for farmers and a staple food for consumers. The crop is the third largest vegetable crop after potato and tomato, but its prices are most volatile in Indian markets.

India ranked as the second-largest tomato producer globally, following China, and contributed about 10.52% to the world's total tomato production. India cultivated tomatoes over approximately 7.74 lakh hectares, yielding a total production of 20.34 million tons in the fiscal year 2022-23 (pib.gov.in).

Tomato produce comes into market immediately after harvesting, and being a highly perishable commodity. It is extensively susceptible to price variations in the market implying that the produce should be immediately sold and cleared from the market without any delay. In India, tomatoes are grown in various states across the country, and there are several major markets where they are traded and distributed. These markets serve as crucial nodes in the tomato supply chain, connecting producers with wholesalers, retailers, and consumers across the country. India's diverse ago-climatic conditions allow for tomato cultivation across different regions, contributing to its status as one of the world's largest producers of tomatoes. Several states play a vital role in tomato production, supplying substantial volumes to both domestic and international markets and support export markets.

The variation in the market Arrivals and Prices can be classified, as Temporal variation and Spatial variation. Temporal variations arise from a complex mix of cyclical, seasonal, and irregular factors, with the seasonal component being the most significant. The trends in Arrivals and Prices are the changes over years and observed in the long run. The study of trends enables us to indicate the general direction of change in arrivals and prices in different markets over a period of time. The Seasonal variation is a regularly recurring pattern that is completed generally once in twelve months. Cyclical variations in market arrivals and prices are the continuous cycles, usually initiated by some exogenous forces. The knowledge of such cycle

helps us in protecting the economy against violent fluctuations. The relationship between price movements in different markets largely depends on the level of competition, the dissemination of market information, and the behavior of market participants. Analyzing these relationships helps us understand the efficiency of the marketing system.

Understanding the temporal variation in the arrivals and prices of tomatoes in major Indian markets is a critical area of study due to its significant impact on both producers and consumers. These markets, being key hubs for tomato trade, exhibit distinct patterns in terms of supply and pricing influenced by various factors including seasonal production cycles, weather conditions, and market demand. This study focuses on major markets such as Madanpalle, Kolar, Azadpur, Pimpalgaon, and Ahmedabad, which are significant centers for tomato trade in India. By analyzing data from 2012 to 2022, this research aims to provide insights into the factors influencing market behavior and suggest strategies for improving market efficiency and farmer income. The present topic entitled "Temporal Variations in Arrival and Prices of Tomato in major markets of India" has been purposively taken to examine the trends, variation, seasonal and cyclical fluctuations in tomato arrivals and prices and to propose effective measures for minimizing this volatility, price risk and protect price security of farming community for tomato crop, adopting long term procurement policies and recommend suitable policies for improving tomato marketing in the study area.

The study was undertaken with the following objectives:

- 1) To study the Trend and Variations in Arrival and Prices of Tomato.
- 2) To workout Seasonal Indices of Arrival and Prices of Tomato.
- 3) To estimate Cyclical Indices of Arrival and Prices of Tomato.
- 4) To study the relationship between Arrival and Prices of Tomato.

Materials and Methods

The present study was based only on secondary data. The data was collected from

the government website of Agmark net. The data on Arrival and Prices were collected from the five major Tomato Market in India namely Madanpalle, Azadpur, Kolar, Pimpalgaon and Ahmedabad. The data were collected for the period of 10 years from the year of 2012-13 to 2022-23. The collected data was analyzed by using different analytical technique which are as follows:

Trend and Variation in Arrival and Prices of Tomato:**Compound Growth Rate:**

In present study the compound growth rates in arrival and prices of tomato were estimated as follows:

The exponential equation of the following types was used:

$$Y = ab^t \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

where,

Y=Arrival and Prices,

a =Intercept or constant,

b = Trend coefficient/Regression,

t = Time variable.

This equation was estimated after transforming (1) as follows:

$$\text{Log } Y = \text{Log } a + t \text{ Log } b \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Annual Compound Growth rate in percentage is calculated as:

$$\text{CGR } (\%) = [\text{Antilog } (\text{Log } b)-1] \times 100$$

Coefficient of variation:

Coefficient of variation in prices and arrivals was computed to see the variation and predict the behavior of prices and arrival whether they are stable involving less risk and uncertainty and vice-versa.

$$\text{CV} = \frac{\sigma}{\bar{x}} \times 100$$

Where,

σ = Standard deviation

\bar{x} = Arithmetic mean.

Cuddy-Delle Valle Instability index:

To check the variability in arrival and prices, Cuddy-Della Valle index (CDVI) was used as follows:

$$\text{CDVI } (\%) = \text{CV} \sqrt{(1 - R)^2}$$

Where,

CV=coefficient of variation,

$$\sqrt{(1 - R)^2} = \text{Adjusted coefficient of multiple determination.}$$

Seasonal Indices in Arrival and Prices of Tomato:

The Seasonal indices of arrival and Prices of Tomato was worked out by using the simple moving average method, as follows:

$$\text{SI} = \frac{\text{Monthly average of arrival and prices} \times 100}{\text{Average of monthly average}}$$

Cyclical indices of Arrival and Prices of Tomato:

Cyclical indices were calculated for the arrival and prices of Tomato from the multiplicative model of time series data, as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Cyclical indices} &= \text{Original yearly value} \times 100 \\ &= T \times C \times I \times \frac{\text{Estimated trend value} \times 100}{T} \\ &= (C \times I) \times 100 \end{aligned}$$

Where,

T=Trend,

C=Cyclical component,

I=Irregular component.

Correlation between Arrival and Prices of Tomato:

The correlation is the measure of degree of relationship amongst two series i.e. Arrival and Prices. The formula used for calculating the correlation (r_{xy}) is as follows.

$$r_{xy} = \frac{\text{Cov } x, y}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}$$

Where,

r = correlation coefficient,

x = Arrival Mean,

y = Prices,

Cov(x,y) = Co-variance between x and y,

σ_x = standard deviation of x,

σ_y = standard deviation of y.

Result and Discussions

Trend and Variation in Arrival and Prices of Tomato :

Compound Growth Rate (CGR):

The results of Compound Annual Growth Rates for Arrivals and Prices of Tomato for the period from 2012-22 are estimated and presented for Madanpalle, Azadpur, Kolar, Pimpalgaon and Ahmedabad markets in Table 1:

Table 1: Compound Growth Rates (CGR) in Arrival and Prices of Tomato in Major Markets of India (2012-22):

Major markets	Arrival		Prices	
	CGR	't' value	CGR	't' value
Madanpalle	0.75 ^{ns}	0.05	0.82**	2.15
Azadpur	0.08 ^{ns}	1.07	0.27**	2.28
Kolar	1.73***	9.95	0.24**	1.77
Pimpalgaon	-0.48 ^{ns}	-0.5	0.2 ^{ns}	0.7
Ahmedabad	-0.26**	-1.9	0.59***	3.62

(Note: ***, ** denotes significance at 1 and 5 per cent respectively and ns indicates non- significance).

The Compound Growth Rates (CGR) of Tomato arrivals and prices across major markets in India from 2012 to 2022 presents varied trends. In Madanpalle, the arrival growth rate is positive at 0.75 per cent, but it is statistically non-significant, whereas prices have grown by 0.82 per cent (significant at 5 per cent level), indicating a moderate rise in prices. Azadpur shows minimal growth in arrivals by 0.08 per cent, that is not significant, but prices have increased by 0.27 per cent (significant growth at 5 per cent level). Kolar stands out with a strong and highly significant growth in arrivals at 1.73 per cent (significant at 1 per cent), and prices have also grown by 0.24 per cent (significant at 5 per cent level). In Pimpalgaon, both arrivals (-0.48 per cent) and prices (0.2 per cent) show non-significant changes, with arrivals declining slightly. Ahmedabad exhibits a significant decline in arrivals by -0.26 per cent, but prices have risen substantially by 0.59 per cent (significant at 1 per cent level).

Overall, while prices have generally increased across most markets, the trends in arrivals are mixed. Kolar shows the most robust growth in arrivals, whereas Ahmedabad experiences a notable decline. Despite varying arrival trends, the rise in prices across the markets, especially in Ahmedabad, Madanpalle, and Azadpur, reflects growing consumer

costs for tomatoes.

Coefficient of variation (CV):

Variability in Arrival and Prices of Tomato in major markets of India were worked out for the period 2012 to 2022 shown in Table 2 and Table 3 respectively:

The table 2 presents the variability (CV%) in tomato arrivals across major Indian markets from 2012 to 2022, for each market. Madanpalle shows the highest variability in 2015 with a CV of 202.72 per cent, indicating significant fluctuations, while the lowest CV is 28.25 per cent in 2014. Azadpur has the lowest overall variability, with its CV ranging from 11.79 per cent in 2018 to 86.53 per cent in 2022, suggesting more stable tomato arrivals compared to other markets. Kolar experiences considerable variability, with a peak CV of 122.49 per cent in 2015 and a low of 49.54 per cent in 2017. Pimpalgaon displays consistently high variability, with a maximum CV of 150.71 per cent in 2016 and a minimum of 78.04 per cent in 2012. Ahmedabad also shows substantial fluctuations, with the highest CV of 164.59 per cent in 2021 and the lowest at 33.52 per cent in 2013. Overall, Madanpalle and Ahmedabad exhibit the most extreme variability, while Azadpur remains the most stable market during the period.

The table 3 shows the variability (CV%), in tomato prices across major Indian markets from 2012 to 2022, for each market. Madanpalle exhibits the highest price variability in 2022 with a CV of 115.81 per cent, while the lowest is 6.49 per cent in 2019, indicating significant price swings. Azadpur shows moderate variability, with the highest CV of 67.53 per cent in 2021 and the lowest at 17.04 per cent in 2015, suggesting relatively stable prices in most years. Kolar has a wide range of price variability, peaking at 92.85 per cent in 2021 and reaching a low of 24.13 per cent in 2018, indicating fluctuations in pricing stability. Pimpalgaon shows substantial price swings, with a

maximum CV of 87.79 per cent in 2012 and a minimum of 24.65 per cent in 2020. Ahmedabad experiences significant price variability, with the highest CV of 94.98 per cent in 2021 and the lowest at 37.03 per cent in 2019. Overall, Madanpalle and Ahmedabad demonstrate the greatest price volatility, while Azadpur maintains more consistent pricing over the years.

Cuddy Della Valle Index (CDVI):

The variability of both arrival and prices of tomato has been calculated using Cuddy Della Valle Index. The result is presented in Table 4:

Table 4: Variability (CDVI) in Arrival and Prices of Tomato in Major Markets of India (2012-2022):

Sr. no.	Major markets	CDVI (%):	
		Arrival:	Prices:
1.	Madanpalle	85.06	42.80
2.	Azadpur	30.75	47.04
3.	Kolar	55.38	53.40
4.	Pimpalgaon	128.11	46.91
5.	Ahmedabad	55.77	58.60

The table 4 presents the variability (CDVI) for tomato arrivals and prices across major Indian markets from 2012 to 2022. Pimpalgaon exhibits the highest variability in arrivals with a CDVI of 128.11%, indicating significant fluctuations in supply. In contrast, Azadpur has the lowest arrival variability at 30.75%, suggesting a more stable supply over the years. Regarding prices, Ahmedabad shows the highest variability with a CDVI of 58.60%, reflecting considerable price swings, while Madanpalle has the lowest price variability at 42.80%. Overall, the data indicates that Pimpalgaon is the most unstable market in terms of arrivals, while Ahmedabad experiences the greatest price fluctuations, with Azadpur and Madanpalle showing relatively more stability.

Seasonal indices of Arrivals and Prices of Tomato in Major Markets of India (2012-2022):

The seasonal indices of monthly average of arrivals and prices in Madanpalle, Azadpur, Kolar, Pimpalgaon, and Ahmedabad markets were worked out to study the seasonal variations as shown in Table 5:

Seasonal indices of monthly Arrival of Tomato (2012-2022):

Table 5 indicates that the higher indices of market arrivals of tomato were observed 1999.43 in the month of July in Kolar market, followed by 399.53 in September month in Pimpalgaon market, 194.95 in August month in Madanpalle market, 130.18 in June month in Ahmedabad market and 123.30 in March month in Azadpur market. However, the lower indices of market arrivals of tomato were observed 0.14 in the month of May in Pimpalgaon market, followed by 43.87 in March month in Madanpalle market, 54.99 in February month in Ahmedabad market, 78.23 in March month in Azadpur market and 351.14 in the month of July in Kolar market.

Seasonal indices of monthly Prices of Tomato (2012-2022):

Table 5 indicates that the highest price indices of tomato were observed 177.83 in Ahmedabad market, followed by 176.87 in Pimpalgaon market, 162.19 in Madanpalle market, 145.03 in Kolar market and 143.74 in Azadpur market overall during July Month. However, the lowest price indices of tomato were observed 39.04 in the month of February in Madanpalle market, followed by 46.28 in May month in Pimpalgaon market, 47.67 in March month in Ahmedabad market, 57.54 in May month in Azadpur market and 60.31 in the month of March in Kolar market.

Cyclical indices of Arrival and Prices of Tomato in Major Markets of India (2012-22):

The cyclical indices were worked out for the period 2012 to 2022 for

five major markets, i.e., Madanpalle, Azadpur, Kolar, Pimpalgaon, and Ahmedabad markets of Tomato in India and presented in Table 6.

The table 6 presents the cyclical indices for tomato arrivals and prices across major markets in India from 2012 to 2022, illustrating the yearly fluctuations in both arrival and prices. In Madanpalle, arrivals show a steady increase, reaching a peak cyclical index of 109.88 in 2022, while prices also trend upward, culminating at 138.20 in the same year. Azadpur experiences a decline in arrivals from 2017, dropping to 89.90 in 2022, although prices remain relatively stable, with a notable high of 127.39 in 2021. Kolar demonstrates a downward trend in both arrivals and prices, with arrivals decreasing to 53.15 in 2022 and prices falling to 85.07, reflecting significant challenges in supply. Pimpalgaon shows a more volatile pattern, with prices peaking at 123.24 in 2015 before declining sharply to 67.96 in 2022, while arrivals fluctuate moderately. In Ahmedabad, arrivals decline consistently to 53.15 in 2022, while prices exhibit a downward trend, reaching 79.99.

Overall, the cyclical indices highlight significant fluctuations in tomato markets across India, with Madanpalle maintaining the most consistent upward trend in both arrivals and prices, while Kolar and Ahmedabad show notable declines, indicating instability in their tomato supply and pricing over the years.

IV. Correlation between Arrival and Prices of Tomato in Major Markets of India (2012 to 2022):

The analysis of the correlation between arrivals and prices were worked out for the period 2012 to 2022 for five major markets, i.e., Madanpalle, Azadpur, Kolar, Pimpalgaon, and Ahmedabad markets of Tomato in India and presented in Table 7:

The table presents the correlation coefficients between tomato arrivals and prices in major markets across India from 2012 to 2022, all of which indicate non-significance. In Madanpalle, the correlation coefficient is -0.05, suggesting a very weak negative relationship between arrivals and prices. Azadpur shows a similar trend with a correlation coefficient of -0.01, indicating almost no relationship. Kolar and Ahmedabad exhibit correlation coefficients of 0.01 and 0.03, respectively, both reflecting minimal positive relationships, yet lacking statistical significance. Pimpalgaon has the highest correlation coefficient at 0.15, indicating a slightly stronger positive association between arrivals and prices, but still not significant, as indicated by its t-value of 0.47. Overall, the correlation values across these markets

suggest that fluctuations in tomato arrivals do not significantly influence prices.

Conclusion

The Compound Growth Rates (CGR) highlight significant Trends in Tomato markets. The Trends in the Growth Rates of Tomato Arrivals and Prices show mixed results across major markets. In Madanpalle, while Arrivals showed no significant growth, prices experienced a significant positive growth rate. Azadpur had stable arrivals but a notable rise in prices. Kolar exhibited strong growth in both arrivals and prices. Pimpalgaon saw no significant change in either arrivals or prices, while Ahmedabad experienced a slight decline in arrivals but significant positive growth in Prices. This indicates varied market dynamics across regions.

The variability (CV) in tomato arrivals across major Indian markets from 2012 to 2022, shows significant fluctuations in arrivals in several markets, with some markets experiencing high variability, indicating instability in supply, while others display relatively consistent patterns. Markets like Pimpalgaon and Kolar show considerable volatility over the years, suggesting irregular supply conditions. In contrast, markets like Azadpur and Ahmedabad show more stable arrival patterns with lower variability. Conversely, the variability (CV) in tomato prices across major Indian markets from 2012 to 2022, revealed that there is notable price volatility in markets like Madanpalle and Pimpalgaon, where fluctuations are more pronounced, reflecting unstable pricing trends. In contrast, markets such as Kolar and Azadpur exhibit relatively moderate price variability, indicating more stable pricing over the years. However, there are instances where variability spikes, as seen in some years in Ahmedabad, showing inconsistency in pricing across different regions.

The Cuddy Della Valle Index data indicates that the highest variability in Tomato Arrivals, while Madanpalle exhibited significant arrival variability as well. Prices were most volatile in Ahmedabad and Kolar. In general, arrival variability was higher than price variability in most markets except Ahmedabad, indicating fluctuating market conditions in arrivals, while prices remained more stable comparatively.

The Seasonal index of Arrivals revealed that Tomato Arrivals were lowest during February-

May months in all the markets and highest market arrivals were observed during July– September months in all markets except Azadpur market which was observed in March month. Price indices were lowest in February– March in all the markets while it was highest during July month in all the major markets of India.

The cyclical fluctuations in tomato arrivals and prices across major markets in India from 2012 to 2022, showcases that, in Madanpalle, prices generally trended upward, while arrivals remained relatively stable. Azadpur market experienced moderate fluctuations in both arrivals and prices, with a slight upward trend in prices. Kolar and Pimpalgaon markets saw a notable decline in arrivals over time, while prices fluctuated but generally increased. In Ahmedabad, price levels rose steadily, while arrivals showed more stability compared to other markets.

Correlation coefficients indicated that in Madanpalle, positive

correlation in 2018 was seen with a significant negative correlation in 2022, indicating price fluctuations with arrivals. In Azadpur, significant negative correlation in 2013, 2016, and 2017 was seen, showing an inverse relationship between Arrivals and Prices. In Kolar, significant positive Correlation in 2017, 2018, and 2020 was seen, suggesting simultaneous increases in Arrivals and Prices. In Pimpalgaon and Ahmedabad, both markets showed significant positive Correlations in certain years, with notable increases in both variables during peak years.

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